

EFFECTIVE USE OF TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN THE WORLD'S TOP 1000 UNIVERSITIES

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Annotation: This paper considers some modern methods of teaching foreign languages in prestigious universities of the world, in terms of using computer technologies, specifically utilizing online applications in language learning. The purpose of this article is to emphasize the importance of using modern technologies to improve the quality of teaching foreign languages to students. Furthermore, the article provides information about the advantages and possibilities of using this technology in the educational process in higher education institutions.

Keywords: Social networking, Collaborative learning, learning languages

Many researchers believe that educational technologies are one of the ways to implement a personal active approach to learning in the classroom, as a result of which students act as active creative subjects. Currently, there is a distinction between two components of the term content: educational technologies (Education technology) and technology in education (Technology in education). Using the first term, they represent the methods of scientific organization of the teacher's work, with the help of which the set goals of education are best achieved, and using the second, the use of technical means of teaching educational process which makes the learning process both enjoyable and multifunctional. The latter component will be under discussion in the current paper.

Types of methods: Collaborative learning: This educational technology is based on the idea of the interaction of students in a group of classes, the idea of mutual education, in which students do not only individually solve educational problems, but also take collective responsibility, help each other and provide collective support accountability for each student's success. Unlike frontal and individual education, the student works as an individual subject of educational activity, is responsible only "for himself", for his successes and failures, and the relationship with the teacher is subjective during training, conditions for cooperation and mutual cooperation are created and actualization of the collective subject of cooperation and educational activity in the "student-teacher-group system" is carried out.

Technology brings the world to the classroom; the times are changing and education together with the society enhances students' motivation. Effective language teachers should be enthusiastic and creative because language learners can lose their motivation and desire easily (Ellis, 1997:56). Providing learners with optimal learning conditions and opportunities to meet the standards for language learning is only part of the instructional technology. It is essential for teachers to also consider how to use technology so that it supports effective learning. In this context, it is also very important not to overwhelm the class with technology since students will fail to recognize the benefits of that particular technology for language learning. In addition, just by simply using a specific technological tool in the classroom one

cannot guarantee increase in students' learning and attention in the class. (Daniela Kirovska-Simjanoska, 2017).

There is an instruction in English for Specific Purposes (ESP):

- 1. Use technology to support the pedagogical goals of the class and curriculum** – Rather than designing instruction to use the technology and to learn technology skills, technology use must be subordinated to the learning goals. In other words, teachers should not use the computer/mobile phone simply for its own sake.
- 2. Make the technology accessible to all learners** - The technology should be used to address the learners' needs and be useful for a variety of instructional purposes. For example, some students prefer visual activities and others prefer verbal ones; hence, technology that allows learners to choose whether information is presented through pictures or written text would meet more students' needs than technology that does not offer learners a choice.
- 3. Use the technology as a tool** - Computers are often said to play at least three roles in the classroom: tutor, teacher, and tool (Levy, 1997). The computer as tutor presents drills and practice, usually with some explanatory rules. The computer cannot actually serve as a teacher, either, because it is not intelligent or capable of individualized, creative feedback. The most useful way to look at technology is as a tool that supports learning in a wide variety of ways.
- 4. Use technology effectively** - Effective means that students learn language better or faster using the technology than they would have using the tools that would ordinarily available.
- 5. Use technology efficiently** - Efficient indicates that technology accomplishes learning goals with less time and work for teachers and learners (Egbert, 2005). Educators are required to work out technology-based activities that are short, and meaningful since the classroom time is limited.

Technology has been utilized in ESP instruction since the introduction of the computer into the classroom, throughout the development of Internet and the World Wide Web and to the very invention of mobile and cloud-computing technologies. According to Bloch (2013), technology in ESP teaching has provided access to authentic texts and has been used as a tool for helping with traditional (face-to-face) type of language learning. It has been used as an ESP repository for authentic materials such as online newspapers and magazines, news broadcasts, lectures, etc. Technology has furthermore helped bringing relevant language experience from outside and has helped teachers to utilize authentic materials such as digital media (Facebook, Twitter) etc., within the classroom setting, providing students with opportunities to engage in significant and genuine discourses related to their areas of study.

Technology also offers various visualization tools that can be used in language learning (Krajka, 2015). When it comes to ESP instruction, these tools can be utilized for content and topics visualization, as well as for the vocabulary learning. The use of technology in ESP instruction has revolutionized the ways ESP materials developers and course designers produce learning materials for ESP instruction (Butler-Pascoe, 2009). Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998) suggest that ESP is an independent and a separate activity and has its own ESP research agenda within the field of applied linguistics. Furthermore, ESP instruction has its own methodology and its research is interdisciplinary. Therefore, it is a fallacy to generalize the findings of the use of technology in EFL contexts to the field of ESP instruction.

Summing up the previous research one can conclude that the research on technology and ESP instruction is still at the beginning stages. There are a number of topics and technologies that

have not been adequately researched. More needs to be done, specifically innovative and inventive applications need to be further investigated and examined. According to Bloch (2013) another key problem that has to be researched more is how to put into practice new technologies that are continually being introduced. He believes that the choice of the most suitable technology in the ESP classroom depends on various factors, the most important of them being the problem the teacher wants to address, and/or the learning objective that needs to be accomplished, which in numerous cases involves a belief that learning to use the technology itself can fulfill the needs of the learner.

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